

BENTHIC RESOURCES ASSESSMENT TECHNIQUE, A METHOD FOR QUANTIFYING THE EFFECTS
OF BENTHIC COMMUNITY CHANGES ON FISH RESOURCES

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Abstract

Preoperational baseline characterizations and postoperational monitoring strategies associated with dredged material disposal in the coastal zone commonly document changes in sediment and benthic invertebrate communities inhabiting those sediments. The U.S. Army Engineer Waterways Experiment Station is developing and field-testing a technique that uses benthic invertebrate community data to make quantitative statements about the feeding habitat value to fish of natural bottoms and bottoms modified by dredged material disposal or other activities influencing substrate quality.

The technique, called Benthic Resources Assessment Technique (BRAT), employs two different types of information from a project area. A list of the bottom-feeding fishes inhabiting a project area is used to select the benthic resources important to an impact assessment. As the first step, observations and measurements of the morphology of specimens of these species are carried through a data reduction and analysis sequence that assigns each fish to a feeding strategy class or guild that appears to correlate with potential prey size and a prey's location (depth) below the sediment surface. The second step involves the analysis of information from a benthic macroinfaunal invertebrate community survey. The BRAT then classifies the invertebrate taxa according to their size and the distribution of their biomass relative to the sediment surface. Estimates of standing crop complement this classification scheme. When combined, the two types of information provide an estimate of the potential prey biomass (grams/meter squared) or energy (kilocalories/meter squared) available to the fish in a particular feeding guild.

This technique facilitates the development of a quantitative impact statement using data on changes in the benthos related to project activities. Additionally it allows quantitative comparison to be made between areas being considered for disposal and/or other modification during project planning and uses a measure with social significance (i.e., the potential productivity of the demersal fishery).

1. Introduction

The most difficult and important part of environmental impact analysis is interpreting the relationship between documented community changes and environmental processes or natural biological resources important to man. Boesch et al (in review) makes the statement "One could take the view that any modification of a marine ecosystem which is attributable to human activities is to be avoided and thus avoid addressing the 'so what' question facing the applied ecologist and manager." But Boesch also identifies a consideration of all resource management decisions when he states that if this view were applied as a general rule, it would eliminate many culturally acceptable uses of the marine environment.

National legislation such as the Marine Protection, Research and Sanctuaries Act (Public Law 92-532) and international agreements like the London Dumping Convention contain directives to resource managers with responsibilities for permitting activities related to ocean disposal. Public Law 92-532 contains criteria to guide determinations that dumping will not unreasonably degrade or endanger human health, welfare or amenities or the marine environment, ecological systems or economic potentialities. More specific considerations in the law include the effects of dumping on: potential changes in marine ecosystem diversity, productivity and stability; species and community population dynamics and; the fishery resource.

Lacking in the national and international legislative guidance is information on procedures that should be used to determine potential changes in conditions like ecosystem productivity and stability and effects on the fishery resource and for relating those changes and effects to human interests. The provision of that information remains the responsibility of applied ecology.

This paper concerns the implications of changes in the macroinvertebrate benthos to fish habitat values and is presented with the contention that changes in a benthic macroinvertebrate community related to a project are not perceived as important to man unless they involve commercially, recreationally or legally protected

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invertebrate species or unless they can be linked to other biological resources having human importance, such as fish. No procedures will be discussed for identifying the commercial, recreational or legal status of a benthic invertebrate. This information exists in extant sources, readily available to anyone who needs it. Much more difficult to ascertain is the linkage between benthic invertebrates and fishes. This linkage and procedures for quantifying it are the principal topic of this paper.

The question can be logically asked: If its fish we're interested in, why not study the fish community directly? There are advantages in using fish community information to assess environmental impacts. Karr (1981) lists some of these as the availability of life history information, the representation of a variety of trophic levels, ease of identification, social relevance, ubiquity and applicability to the fishable waters mandate of Congress. Karr (1981) also identifies disadvantages of monitoring fish due to the selective nature of sampling, manpower needs for field sampling, and fish mobility on diel and seasonal time scales. Another disadvantage can be added to these. It is the inefficiency of the otter trawl, the quantitative fish sampling device most commonly used in estuarine and marine fish community studies. Kjelson and Johnson (1978) reported highly variable catch efficiencies using a 6.1 meter trawl. Catch efficiencies for pinfish and spot averaged around 48 and 32 percent respectively. Loesch et al (1976) reported trawl efficiencies of 30-50 percent for brown shrimp, 26 percent for croaker and only 6 percent for spot.

Contrasted with fishes, benthic macroinvertebrates as a study group possess a different suite of advantages and disadvantages. Invertebrate macrobenthos are regarded to be good indicators of environmental alterations because of the quasi two-dimensional nature of benthic habitats which simplify sampling, their sedentary nature, their relative longevity requiring a tolerance to temporally variable environmental conditions resulting in their ability to reflect "integral" conditions (Boesch et al in review), and their susceptibility to physical and chemical alterations of the bottom sediment. Compared with fishes, life history information for benthos is generally less available and identification generally more difficult excepting circumstances involving well studied species of commercial or recreational importance or existing as ubiquitous community dominants. But the problems caused by the disadvantages of studying benthic macroinvertebrate communities for environmental assessment seem more tractable than is the case with fishes. The availability of good benthic invertebrate life history information and identification aids will continue to improve with time; the inefficiency of fish sampling gear used in estuarine and marine systems and the spatially and temporally variable nature of fish data seem more persistent and serious problems.

So environmental impact analysts typically find themselves with a dilemma having the following characteristics:

- (a) the availability of good, quantitative benthic community data documenting changes in the species composition, abundances and weights of benthic invertebrate taxa which although correlated with environmental alteration by man, seem to lack obvious importance to man.
- (b) The availability of fish community data documenting changes in the species composition, abundances and weights of fishes, but which has very limited value for making defensible quantitative statements about fish habitat quality.

A solution to the dilemma is being explored through efforts in progress at the U.S. Army Engineer Waterways Experiment Station (WES). The Benthic Resources Assessment Project at the WES is developing and field testing a technique that uses benthic invertebrate data to make quantitative statements about the food-value of benthic habitats to demersal bottom-feeding fishes.

The importance of the macrobenthos as food for bottom-feeding fishes and the implications for demersal fish production are well discussed in the literature. Mills (1980) constructed a conceptual model and computed both pelagic and benthic energy flows to explain the differences between continental shelf and slope ecosystems off the coast of Nova Scotia. One system produced demersal fish while pelagic fish were primarily produced by the other. Among the conclusions of his complex analysis is that depth is a factor that governs the speed and routing of primary production to the bottom, thereby influencing benthic secondary production and demersal fish production as a function of production by the invertebrate benthos. There are two sizeable categories of published information that provide evidence of the important trophic linkage between the benthos and bottom-feeding fishes. The first of these provides the direct evidence of invertebrate consumption by fishes in the form of fish stomach contents data (Darnell 1958, Bass and Avault 1975, Heard 1975, Brook 1977, Chao and Musick 1977, Desselle et al 1978, Overstreet and Heard 1978, and many others); the second discusses changes in the types, numbers and weights of invertebrates affected by fish and invertebrate predations (Peer 1970, Trevallion et al 1970, Virnstein 1977, 1979, Arntz 1980).

With the discovery of the existence of this important trophic link between the measurable "less important to man" benthic invertebrate community and the harder-to-measure, "more important to man" fish community, we are faced with the difficult requirement sited at the very beginning of this discussion - i.e. the interpretation of the relationship between the two.

The time-honored procedure used to determine which benthos are eaten by fishes has been food habits studies. Traditional food habits studies will continue to produce important data leading us toward a better understanding of fishes rations and feeding behaviors. The traditional approach has been applied in both field (Peer 1970, Heard 1975, Ross 1977, Overstreet and Heard 1978) and laboratory (Ivlev 1961) studies to reveal that the same species of fish changes its diet as it increases in size (Hodson et al 1981), that the diet of a fish species inhabiting different locations will differ at each location (Overstreet and Heard 1978), and that the diet of a fish will switch in apparent response to the seasonal food availability defined by the changing abundance of food items (Powell and Schwartz 1979). If traditional food habits information for fishes inhabiting an environmental assessment study area were available in a way that considered the different food requirements of different size classes, as well as the plasticity of the diet of a size class seasonally and spatially, then interpretation of the consequences of changing the benthos would be possible. But an obvious problem exists that becomes quickly apparent to anyone aware of the amount of time and money needed to develop such comprehensive information: food habits studies are expensive and time consuming (Word 1978).

A variety of procedures, published and in different stages of development have been proposed to reduce the cost or increase the ease of making statements about fish feeding and feeding habitat value. The simplest perhaps, described by Borgeson (1963) reduces the cost of food habits studies by combining the contents of the stomachs of a number of individuals of the same species and size and analyzing a subsampled volume of the pooled diets. This permits a description of the feeding habit of the whole size class, pools much of the variability within the size class and significantly reduces the time and cost of analysis. A significant departure from the traditional method has been described by Feller et al (1978) who used immunological analysis of predator tissues to describe the diets of marine soft bottom benthos. Word (1979) described a procedure for computing the "Infaunal Trophic Index" which determines the relative importance of different invertebrate feeding strategies for soft-bottom communities. It divides invertebrates into four feeding categories that are related to the amount of organic material in sediments and correlated with certain vertical distribution patterns. Word (1978) described the application of the Infaunal Trophic Index concept for studying the feeding habits of soft-bottom benthic fish species as well as estimating dietary overlap in multispecies fisheries. The analysis requires a comparison between the food habits of fish species of interest and the benthic community of the potential foraging area. A comparison of the index value of the fish diet with the index value of the benthic community is used to determine the "value" of a particular community to the particular fish. The Benthic Resource Assessment Technique (BRAT) being developed at WES differs from both the more tra-

ditional methods and the other less traditional procedures primarily by its lack of requirement for actual food habits information and its incorporation of size selection. Food habits data obtained using Borgeson's (1963) technique are being used for testing and verifying the BRAT but are not viewed as being a requirement of the final methodology.

2. Benthic Resource Assessment Technique

Application of the BRAT to a project area, requires the integration of information from two different sources.

A list of bottom feeding (demersal) fishes likely to occur in a project area is used to select target species of commercial, recreational, or ecological importance for evaluation of trophic support potential, using the BRAT. A morphological analysis routine is conducted using specimens from each species and size class selected, and ultimately assigns fish to a feeding guild based on similarities in feeding habits (i.e. prey size and maximum depth of exploited benthic infaunal prey). The morphological analysis routine consists of observations and measurements of some 15 meristic and 46 nonmeristic external, dentition, and gill raker characters known to be potentially important in feeding (Clarke in press). Each morphological character is being evaluated in current field verification studies, to identify the individual characters and/or suites of characters which correlate highly with discrimination of prey size and feeding depth within the sediments (available zone). Our laboratory studies have generally found that measurements of between 5 and 8 individual fish per size class are sufficient to stabilize the mean for a meristic character (Figure 1). Laboratory studies have also confirmed

SEA CATFISH: SIZE CLASS 2 (10-14.9 cm)

Effect of Sample Size on the Mean Inter-Raker Distance
Figure 1

considerable intraspecific and interspecific differences in a given meristic character such as raker length (Figure 2). Characters such as

Dependence of a Meristic Character on Species and Size Class
Figure 2

inter-raker distance have been found to be significantly correlated with prey size as shown by an examination of the relationship between prey size and inter-raker distance in the sea catfish (*Ariopsis felis*) (Figure 3). Numerical classi-

Relation Between Inter-Raker Distance and Average Prey Size
Figure 3

fication (Boesch 1977) of those characters identified through correlation analysis as best discriminating prey size and feeding depth can be used to group fish species and individual size classes into feeding assemblages or guilds. Thereafter, a valuation of a given target fish species within a feeding guild using the BRAT can be used to describe all other species associated with that guild. A table listing each predator's range of potential prey sizes and maximum feeding depth in

sediments (available zone) will be generated following the field verification work that is described in a later section of this paper. An example of interspecific prey size selectivity is illustrated by Table 1 for two demersal predators

Table 1

PREY SIZE* SELECTIVITY FOR DEMERSAL PREDATOR FISH (SIZE CLASS: 10-15 CM-SL) FEEDING FROM THE SAME GENERAL HABITAT

PREY TAXA	SPOT	PERCENT	SEA CATFISH	PERCENT
Polychaeta	0.16	4.6	14.9	85.9
Crustacea	0.15	11.9	3.5	13.8
Cumacea	0.24	51.6	-----	0.0
Meiofauna	0.014	18.4	-----	0.0
Mollusca	8.13	8.5	4.8	0.3
Echinodermata	0.77	4.6	-----	-----

*Prey Size Expressed as Mean Individual Weight (mg - Wet Weight)

of the same size class and collected within the same general offshore habitat.

Following the morphological analysis, a benthic community analysis routine is conducted using qualitative and quantitative benthic in-faunal community information from a benthic survey of the project area. The benthic community analysis produces information on the relative sizes of benthic taxa and their quantitative abundances and biomass distribution vertically within the sediment. Each habitat type occurring within the project area is described separately. This information is then coupled with the prey size and maximum feeding depth (available zone) information available from the morphological analysis (Table 2) and the process is reiterated

Table 2

BENTHIC COMMUNITY ANALYSIS*				
PREY TAXA	VULNERABLE SIZE	PROPORTION OF BIOMASS IN AVAILABLE ZONE	BIOMASS/PRODUCTIVITY	POTENTIAL FOOD VALUE
1	+	100%	x	10.0 g/m ² = 10.0 g/m ²
2	+	0%	x	3.1 g/m ² = 0 g/m ²
3	+	50%	x	1.4 g/m ² = 0.7 g/m ²
4	-	85%	x	1.1 g/m ² = 0 g/m ²
•	•	•	•	•
•	•	•	•	•
n	+	70%	x	2.3 g/m ² = 1.6 g/m ²
TOTAL FOOD VALUE				= 12.3 g/m ²

NOTE: The Food Value in g/m² can be Converted to Units of Energy to Compute Potential Fish Production OR to a Suitability Index (Actual/Optimum) Value for Input to a HEP Analysis.

* The Analysis would be Conducted Separately for each Predator Guild (Guild = n Species)

for each feeding guild and habitat type. Additional information such as Production/Biomass (P/B) ratios for each taxa would add additional sophistication to the analysis by improving instantaneous standing crop biomass estimates through an accounting of mortality, reproduction and growth potential. Note that a form of output could be generated (in units of energy or suitability index (SI) units) compatible with the requirements of by the Habitat Evaluation Procedures (USFWS 1980). Figure 4 presents a self

PROCEDURE: USING A HYPOTHETICAL PROJECT

- I. OVERLAY A GRID OF APPROPRIATE, PERHAPS VARIABLE CELL SIZE ON A CHART OF THE PROJECT AREA.
- II. SELECT TARGET SPECIES OR TARGET "GUILDS" OF DEMERSAL BOTTOM-FEEDING FISHES.
- III. FOR EACH TARGET FISH SPECIES OR GUILD, PLOT THE DISTRIBUTIONS OF THE NUMBERS OF INDIVIDUALS, OR BIOMASSES OF "AVAILABLE" BENTHIC INVERTEBRATE TAXA IN EACH CELL BASED ON BENTHIC HABITAT CHARACTERISTICS IN THAT CELL. IF INFORMATION IS AVAILABLE, IMPROVE ESTIMATES OF AVAILABLE BIOMASS BY CONVERSION TO UNITS OF PRODUCTION OR ENERGY.
- IV. SUM VALUES OF "AVAILABLE" INDIVIDUALS, BIOMASS, PRODUCTION OR ENERGY IN A BENTHIC HABITAT TO OBTAIN THE BENTHIC FOOD RESOURCE VALUE OF THAT HABITAT TO A PARTICULAR FISH OR FISH GUILD; SUM VALUES ACROSS HABITATS TO OBTAIN THE VALUE OF THE WHOLE PROJECT AREA.

Applying the BRAT
Figure 4

explanatory example of the application of BRAT using a hypothetical project. An important capability of the technique concerns its ability to permit the tracking of cumulative changes in a project area. For those having environmental assessment responsibilities, this means a determination could be made about the point at which no additional changes should be permitted to occur without violating a predetermined fishery management objective.

3. Field Verification Procedures

Site specific field verification studies are currently underway at WES to evaluate the relationship between morphological characters and their individual and collective ability to describe feeding habits of fishes in terms of: (a) prey size selection, and (b) maximum feeding depth in sediments (available zone).

Size selection studies begin with the analysis of stomach samples from representative size classes of target fish species. Pooled stomach samples describing the feeding habits of a size class associated with a specific habitat type (e.g. coastal margin/mud; open sound/muddy-sand; procedure after Borgeson 1963) are washed through a series of nested 3 inch standard sieves (6.35 mm, 3.35 mm, 2 mm, 1 mm, 0.5 mm and 0.063 mm). The contents of each sieve fraction are enumerated and biomassed by major taxa and the distribution of prey sizes is plotted and evaluated for each sample (Figure 5(1)). This procedure is repeated

Verifying Prey Size Selectivity and the "Available Zone"
Figure 5

for all predator size classes occurring in a particular habitat and the combined matrix of prey size distributions versus predator species/size classes is analyzed by cluster analysis. Output generated from these analyses will classify fish into groups based on similarities in prey size distribution patterns. Additionally, sample statistics on prey size calculated from predator diet information, and including mean, mode, standard deviation and skewness will be correlated with each morphological character individually (Figure 3) and collectively using a stepwise multiple correlation model. Combinations of morphological characters found to be highly correlated with prey size will be classified by cluster analysis and the outputs compared with the food habits cluster analysis output for similarities in feeding guild classifications.

Identification of the available zone or maximum feeding depth in the sediments used by a specific demersal predator will be accomplished by comparing relative prey size distribution patterns in a predator's diet with environmental patterns in a benthic community survey. The comparison will use the information on relative size class distribution patterns of benthic infaunas observed in successive vertical sections of a core sample (i.e. 0-2 cm, 0-5 cm, 0-10 cm, 0-15 cm, 0-20 cm, 0-30 cm) from a given habitat type (Figure 5(2)). Subjectively, pattern recognition between prey size distribution and benthic infaunal size class distribution may identify the available zone (depth: e.g., 0-10 cm), but an objective method is

preferred such as a measurement of feeding selectivity known as the Electivity Index (Ivlev 1961) (Figure 5(3)). The Electivity Index is computed by the formula:

$$E = (r_i - P_i) / (r_i + P_i)$$

where: r_i = relative value of the prey (food) component in the ration of the predator.
 P_i = relative value of the prey (food) component in the environment.

Each successive vertical core will be examined using an Electivity computation (P_i = 0-2 cm, 0-5 cm, 0-10 cm, etc.) and the available zone (i.e. depth) will be identified as that cumulative fraction with the highest positive Electivity Index. It should be noted that the available zone will be expressed in terms of depth and may be modified by sediment quality (i.e. permeability, grain size, etc.). This procedure will be repeated for each additional target species or feeding guild and habitat type to verify the available zone.

Discriminant function analysis (SPSS) will be used to identify the morphological characters which best discriminate feeding guilds identified through cluster analysis. This procedure will help identify the morphological characters most useful for describing prey utilization (i.e. prey size and availability zone = depth) within each feeding guild.

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